

VOID CONTENT IN CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITES AND ITS EFFECTS ON COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES.

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ABSTRACT

A quantitative relationship between void content and compressive strength has been determined for a carbon/epoxy composite material. Flat laminates were automatic tape-layed and cured following standard procedures. Differences in void content were achieved using several pressures during the curing cycle: laminates did not become homogeneous but differences in porosity through the whole part were identified, so it was possible to obtain specimens with different void contents from a single laminate. Areas of different porosity were mapped after an ultrasonic c-scan. Selected specimens were then through-transmission inspected for an accurate measurement of void content. Procedure was calibrated against the density method. Specimens were trimmed down and prepared for modified ASTM D695 compression test. A linear regression was fitted to data for low porosity levels: up to 4% of void content the compressive strength decreases till 60% of ideal strength, at a rate of 10% for each 1% of voids, and beyond this void level the rate of decrease diminished and does not fall under 50%.

Keywords: Porosity, void content, compression test, compressive strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Presence of voids in high performance composite materials for aerospace structures is an unavoidable fact, due to their own nature and to the processing methods. It is necessary to quantify the influence of void content on the mechanical properties of the composite. Otherwise, it is possible to neglect the importance of such defects or, on the other hand, to overvalue their detrimental effect. In the last case, it results in serious economical consequences due to excessively high acceptance levels for critical parts and the use of oversized security factors for design purposes.

Efforts have been made by several researchers to quantify the relationship between void content and mechanical properties [1-3]. Nevertheless, experimental difficulties have shadowed to some extent these attempts. The first reason is that there are not a sufficiently

accurate method for estimation of void content. The second one is the importance of select properly the mechanical test, because some mechanical properties are not so sensitive as others to the presence of voids and so happen with the scattering of test results.

Several methods have been used for the estimation of void content on composites. All have limitation. Density determination is the most widely used, but is a destructive method and it is no possible to perform a mechanical test to the same piece of material that was used for void measurement. Other methods, as the water absorption and radiography, allow to test just the same specimen, but both are very time-consuming procedures and the test-piece must be dried out before testing. Estimation of porosity from micrographs is also feasible, but again the procedure is destructive and, anyway, the surface examination may be unrepresentative of the whole.

We have chosen the ultrasonic inspection method to measure the void level through the material. This is a non-destructive, widely used technique for composites. An average value is obtained of the whole area under the probe, so we have to be sure that the specimen's area of failure has an even void content. It must be, however, calibrated by reference to another method. In this work, the reference method was the density determination one. Ultrasonic estimation of porosity has an overall accuracy that cannot be greater than that of density method, i.e. $\pm 0.5\%$. Values between 0-1% are particularly difficult to assess, so it has no sense to quantify porosity in this range.

The second but no less important experimental difficulty is the selection of mechanical test. The two main properties affected by the presence of voids are: interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and compressive strength and modulus. Other properties like tensile strength and modulus are affected to a fewer extent, because the loss of cross-section due to voids is negligible.

Voids usually are aligned in the fibre direction and reduce fibre/matrix interface. ILSS decreases due to the loss of interfacial area, which plays a fundamental roll in load transfer. But the influence of voids in the decrease of compression properties is much more complex. The mechanisms of failure for different fibre/matrix combinations (mechanical properties of fibre and matrix, interface strength and volume fraction of fibres) are quite different. Microbuckling of fibres is, for example, one of the failures modes more influenced by void content.

We have employed flat laminates cured at several pressures. A wide range of void levels in different zones of the laminate were obtained. We have chosen compression test because it has the smallest area of testing, so it is easier to get an even distribution of voids than in a larger testing area. So, compression specimens were fitted into the small homogeneous areas and was possible to trimmed down a lot of specimens from a single laminate. Nevertheless, scattering in compression test results is great and special care is needed for preparation of specimens [4,5].

For the sake of completeness, test specimens with an unusual high void content have been considered. Anyway, special attention was payed to the more common values (1% to 4%) and a linear regression has been fitted for this range.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Material

The material under research was Hercules[®] AS4/8552. It is a prepreg tape, amine-cured toughened epoxy matrix and reinforced with unidirectional carbon fibres. The reinforcements are AS4 high-strength modulus and high-strain carbon filaments, which are surface treated to increase the composite shear and transverse tensile strength. Resin 8552 is a low-flow system developed to operate in temperature environments of 120°C. ATL tape grade (quality for Automatic Tape Laying) has been used.

2.2. Specimens

Laminates with 6 plies, unidirectional (0°), were automatic tape layed using 150 mm width prepreg tape. Plates were about 260 mm (width) × 360 mm (length) × 1 mm (thickness), with fibre direction aligned with the plate length. To cover the plate width with the tape it was necessary to use two runs by ply; a 1 mm gap was allowed and its position was shifted in every ply (stage) to avoid coincidence of cuts in neighbouring plies.

Hot-plates press was used for curing. Temperature was risen up to 180°C at a rate of 3°C/minute and was held for two hours. Then, it was cooled down to room temperature. Pressure were applied mechanically with the press. No relationship was observed between pressure and void content. Different porosity levels appeared in each single laminate, cured with a unique pressure, so it was possible to cut several test specimens from each panel.

2.3. C-scan ultrasonic inspection

All the panels were inspected by immersion c-scan ultrasonic testing. The most homogeneous ones were candidates to be the reference specimen. Some little specimens were cut and their void content measured by the density determination technique (see paragraph 2.4.). The best panel, with the lowest porosity, was selected as reference. Immersion c-scan was then repeated and areas of different void content (as showed by differences in attenuation) were identified - Figure 1- for each panel.

Compression test specimens were marked on the panel according to the c-scan register.

Figure 1. C-scan showing areas with different void contents.

2.4. Porosity/attenuation calibration

From an other set of panels, a number of little square specimens (10 × 10 mm) were marked and identified. Each specimen was through-

transmission tested and its attenuation measured.

After the inspection, specimens were cut and their density determined as specified in CASA I+D-E-243A [6], in order to estimate void contents -equation (3)-.

$$V_f = \frac{P_2/\rho_f}{P_1/\rho_c} \times 100 \quad (1) \qquad V_R = \frac{P_R/\rho_R}{P_1/\rho_c} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$V_h = 100 - (V_f + V_R) \quad (3)$$

Where V's are % in volume, ρ's are densities (f,R,h refer to fibre, resin and voids, respectively; c refers to laminate), P₁=weight of specimen, P₂=weight of fibre and P_R=weight of resin. A porosity/attenuation calibration curve was derived from data.

2.5. Through-transmission ultrasonic inspection

Specimens for compression test marked on the plates were through-transmission examined and their attenuation respect to the reference specimen measured. Attenuation was related to void content by means of the calibration curve.

Specimen were trimmed down with a diamond disk. Special care was payed to fulfil with the faces parallelism requirements; specimen edges were finished with grinding paper. Four end tabs for load introduction (made of the same material) were hot bonded to the specimens.

2.6. Compression test

Compression test was performed as specified in CASA I+D-E-51 [7]. Test fixture was a modified ASTM D695 type [4]. Ultimate compressive load was measured from the load/displacement register.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 2. Porosity/attenuation calibration curve

Figure 2 shows the porosity/attenuation calibration curve. It must be mentioned that attenuation is expressed in decibels by millimetre of thickness. For our specimens, with a thickness of one millimetre, it is possible to read directly from the graph.

Figure 3 shows compressive strength versus attenuation.

Figure 3. Relationship between compressive strenght and attenuation.

Figure 4 focus on the 0 to 12 dB/mm range. A linear regression has been fitted to these data.

Figure 4. Compressive strenght/attenuation linear regression.

Figure 5 shows the decrease in compressive strength as void content

increases.

Figure 5. Reduction in compressive strength with increasing void content.

In Figure 6, 0% to 4% porosity range is shown. A linear regression has been fitted for these data.

Figure 6. Compressive strength/void content linear regression.

4. DISCUSSION

Void content/through-transmission attenuation relationship shows that an attenuation of 12 dB/mm is related with a porosity of 5% (volume fraction). This level of attenuation is a commonly used rejection criterion for quality purposes. Nevertheless, from the point of view of void content estimated by micrography, 1% is the maximum porosity allowed by several aerospace companies. It looks as both rejection criteria were not equivalent nor coherent.

Regardless of mechanical consideration, all authors agree [1] that it is almost impossible to measure void contents with an overall accuracy better than $\pm 0.5\%$. At the present time, any of the methods can estimate porosity with higher accuracy, and specially at the 0% to 1% range the accuracy is undoubtedly worse. So, a laminate with 1% of nominal void content could have, roughly, from 0% to 2%. The value of 1% is not a milestone, and rejection criteria must be fundamentally based on mechanical considerations.

Both theory predicts and experiment shows that there are a decrease in mechanical properties as void content increases. Qualitatively, the rate of loss of mechanical properties is high for low void contents (up to 5%) and stabilizes for higher values. Then, the residual strength of the laminate does not change appreciably for a wide range of values. At a certain, undetermined porosity level, voids collapse in a continuous debonding and strength falls sharply.

For the most frequently found void levels (up to 4-5%), a linear regression has been obtained -Figure 6-. For 1% of void content a 90% of ideal strength remains, and for 4% the strength is only 60%. So, a decrease of 10% in compressive strength for each 1% of void content is attained. For higher void contents, mechanical losses become stabilized and do not fall under 50% of ideal compressive strength. These results closely agree with those of Yoshida et al. [2] and Hagemaijer and Fassbender [3], for a similar material ($V=1\%$ and 5%, about 92% and 62% of ILSS ideal strength). These authors employ the ILSS test, but the overall trend is the same. Indeed, compression test gives more conservative values than ILSS test does.

For very high void contents (over 20%), residual strength should not remain constant any longer. Void density increase so much that a debonding between plies is obtained, and strength falls sharply. But it is not interesting to know exactly where that upper edge is, due to several reasons: mechanical test of such specimens are very unreliable; void content estimation by ultrasonic attenuation are also very few accurate; the porosity level is not representative of any real part; and last, this upper value depends on laminate thickness.

Anyway, an attenuation level over 12 dB/mm as rejection criterion imply, it seems so, a void content much more higher than the conservative 1% usually specified. If this is true, it should be investigated if the laminate has reached to the part of the curve where a further increase in void content does not mean a great decrease in compressive strength. In this case, the rejection criteria could be soften.

Nevertheless, a hot/wet test program must be carried out to be sure of the lost of mechanical reliability for this material, before to

figure out any change in the usual rejection criteria.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1.- Relationship between compressive strength and ultrasonic attenuation for a CFRP has been investigated. After an experimental correlation between void content and through-transmission ultrasonic attenuation, relationship between compressive strength and void content has been also assessed.

2.- The usual acceptance/rejection value of 12 dB/mm of attenuation does not match with the also usual criteria of 1% of void content. From experimental data, a porosity of, at least, 3% is attained in a laminate with that attenuation.

3.- For 1% of void content a 90% of ideal strength remains in the test specimen, and for 4% the strength is only of 60%. So, a decrease of 10% in compressive strength for each 1% of void content is estimated. For higher void contents, residual strength becomes stabilized and does not fall under 50% of ideal compressive strength.

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